

Review Article

Library and Information Service as Tools for Capacity Building in National Sustainability

Ali Muhammed Fakandu and Kasim Abdullahi
Abdullahi Fodiyo Library Complex, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto,
Nigeria

Abstract

This paper discussed the conceptual definitions of capacity building and its impacts in organisations. The paper also discussed capacity building for librarians and how it enhances library operations. The role of librarians was equally discussed based on the new trends in librarianship. Information services played significant impacts in developing individual and libraries national sustainability. As such, the chapter highlighted some information services rendered in Nigerian libraries such as technical, reference, bibliographic, library cooperation, reprographic extension/community services and it also explain how it affect the capacity building of librarians and the libraries. Information and communication technology (ICT) has radically transformed most of the services provided by a library. ICT is heavily utilized in the storage, processing and dissemination of information. This paper successfully described the application of information and technology (ICT) as enabler in facilitating library services for national sustainability.

Keywords: Information Technology, capacity building, libraries, community services, Nigeria

Introduction

Capacity building refers to the people, institutions, and practices that enable a country to achieve its development objectives. Capacity has both human and institutional dimensions with components such as; skilled human resources, leadership and vision, viable institutions, financial and material resources and effective work practices, including systems, procedures and appropriate incentives (Ogunsola, 2011). According to him, human capacity refers to the individuals capable of performing the tasks necessary for a country to achieve its developmental goals. While, Institutional capacity

refers to the available organizational structure and processes that facilitate the achievement of developmental goals. Adequate capacity engenders self-reliance, and provides an organization and its people the ability to make sound economic choices, create sustainable policies, and solve problems.

Capacity building has great impacts in individual and organization development. According to University of Memphis (2020), capacity building approaches purposefully minimize an over-reliance on outside experts as sources of knowledge, resources, and solutions to community issues. By preventing a dependency relationship on outsiders from forming, capacity building encourages local people to take action on local issues themselves. Capacity building fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment, so that community partners gain greater control over their own future development.

Bolger (2000) stressed that capacity building strengthened confidence, skills, knowledge, and resources that increase from capacity building efforts on one project may enhance a community partner's ability to envision and take action on other projects. Capacity building efforts are sensitive to the particularities of local culture and context, and, as a result, often lead to more feasible and appropriate community solutions than approaches that lack a capacity building focus.

Libraries are built and maintained to provide information resources for a specific and defined community. According to Abubakar (2004), public library serves the residents of a specific geographic region. An academic library serves the students and faculties of a parent college or university. Special libraries support to achieve organizational goals by serving the members. Corporate libraries serve the commercial firms. In each case, the library only exists to serve its parent community. Each library performs three basic functions in the process of serving its community, selecting and collecting information, organizing information, and serving users. In the agricultural university, librarian used the ICT as a tool (such as Library Management Software (LMS), Internet, and Telecommunication etc.) to serve it researcher's right information at the right time. Some librarian suggested four basic functions in the area of library services such as instructing the user about library management. Assisting the users to solve his/her queries, aiding the users in selection of good works and promoting the library within the community. Although over a century has passed, these four functions remain the core of reference and information services in today's digital environment. The primary objective of a library, irrespective of type or size, is to promote the use of its resources. Library services bring together the documents or information sources and their users by personal efforts of the library staff.

Capacity building for Librarians

Capacity building includes man-machine interfaces in organizations. It enhances operating efficiency and skills of personnel, which leads to the excellence of the organization. In libraries, capacity is emphasized in community building. As such, libraries should be able to meet the high-level needs of users, community capacity building woes huge reformation, restructuring, renovation of systems, services and information infrastructures of Library. In accordance with the basic principles of capacity building, Librarians must emerge with new ideas of restructuring and refurbishing their information infrastructure, systems, services and all kinds of library operations to accomplish needs of each and every clientele quickly (Ogunmodede and Mafelu, 2012). Therefore, it is very significant to understand library capacity building for librarians.

Librarians in different type of libraries provide fundamental support to economic growth through direct job creation, contribution to cultural progress of the local area, education, training and skill development, and the enhancement of social capital and social inclusiveness (Mabawonku, 2005). Structure of the libraries plays an important role they are well structured by which information professionals are fascinated. It designates people and resources to the tasks and provides a mechanism for coordination. Hence, for the successful implementation of plans structure is significant.

In order to make them effective and efficient, libraries should take up certain characteristics. Libraries should have a viable plan to increase user services to organize a library into the subject division, allocating professional librarians for different subjects. It is targeted to develop eventually the subject expertise of librarians through their work experience with users. To achieve this new modified organization, the conventional library setting needs to be changed from placing books according to their forms (e.g. monograph publications, periodicals, and reference books), to organizing them according to their subjects (e.g. philosophy, economics, law, physics, computer science). Along with this, the subject librarian will take care of reference services, SDI, Database instruction and selection of books on the same subject. Previously existed a conflict between the book collection, user service librarians and users will be removed through a new setting, which includes interconnection of work within the same subject. This service is user entered and it is a stepping stone to capacity building. Restructuring and organizing present scattering of information and this integrated into a particular subject for its effectiveness.

The conception of library and librarians was started for the purpose to serve the user community. Hence, library professionals were chosen to meet the needs of the users accordingly. This enforced the libraries/librarians to have staff with additional skills so as to deal with the digital library and electronic information environment, along with

which the library professionals should be well aware of the latest technologies and its implication (Mabawonku, 2005). For which, capacity building programmes such as refresher courses, workshops, IT skills acquisition programme, training programs etc. are to be attended by the library professionals. The performance-based evaluation had to be conducted at a regular interval of time so as to help the professionals to acquire the required knowledge and expertise. Hence, the Continuing Educational Programmes (CEPs) has to be made compulsory by the parent institution or deputation of professionals to other institution where the CEPs are conducted. Hence, capacity building of library professional looks towards sustaining reform and development, adapting new skills and technology.

Role of Librarians

The current rapidly changing digital environment has enforced the libraries to adopt the new technology. Considering the trends in the digital environment the librarians must start thinking about the development of new skills and assume the new roles to support technology-based services. Hence, the reference librarian must have the knowledge and skill of accessing and should be able to assist the users in digital information. Technology has created an impact on every aspect of library work. These new trends and development in the ICT have enabled the librarians to rethink on their goals of providing excellent information services to the users. This mission of fulfilling the enhanced information service has become a difficult task on the librarian's part, as most of the libraries are not prepared for rapid change.

The librarian has to be well aware of the organizational and technological changes that are occurring in the library. This helps the librarian to understand the effects of such changes on the organizational structure and on the nature of responsibilities and roles of the library staff. The efforts of the librarian, to manage the change in the library will be supported by a better understanding of the concept of learning organization culture. A learning organization is an organization that continually provides for improvements and can recreate itself as the needs of its users change.

However, the librarians have to continue the investigating on the possible work-based learning activities such as mentoring, benchmarking, coaching, etc. for the library staff to certify that the efforts are being utilized in enhancing skills and personal development of the staff. The inclusion of training to obtain skills in webpage creation, use of electronic resources, Internet, library integrated systems, MS-Office and basic computer skills and personal developments like diversity in the workplace – understanding employees, performance appraisal, building teamwork, total quality improvement leader styles –

applications, planning and organizing, time management etc. are also to be considered in the learning activities (Abubakar, 2004). The introduction of such learning activities into the libraries helps the librarian to identify the specific training needs of both the professional and support staff and the developing of training modules and work-based learning.

Provision of Information Services as tools for Capacity Building

In the modern information society libraries have a new role and there are various types of library models. In the modern society, where the use of electronic services and Web-based information sources constantly increases, libraries are managed in a more democratic way, have more flexible communication system and work organization, and their service development is based on the quality and user-orientation of services. In the modern information society libraries have a new role and there are various types of library models (Mabawonku, 2005). These are as follows: traditional library as a memory institution, library as a learning and research centre, library as a cultural and communication centre, electronic library, digital library and virtual library as library without walls.

Libraries had been performed many important roles in the past agrarian and industrial societies. But those roles were limited in scope. In the 21st century, libraries have to perform pivotal roles in disseminating and sharing the culture of information. In this age of information libraries should be repositories of all of the knowledge and information accumulated by human kind. They will have to store all kinds and forms of material and information and disseminate beyond the geographical boundaries. Today's advanced information technology is enabling libraries to accomplish this immense task.

Exchange of information has always been the most important objectives of libraries. Various systems have been developed to share and exchange the records of human knowledge. Universal Bibliographic Control and Universal Availability of Publications are two major programs of IFLA (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions) to exchange knowledge/information world over. OCLC is the world leading library network in USA for sharing intellectual knowledge among academic community in all over the world.

Umoh (2017) observed that libraries in the 21st century should fulfill more dynamic role. They should exchange knowledge and information with users inside and outside their country, thus going beyond their traditional reference and lending services. This would possible when libraries agreed to expand their roles beyond the geographical boundaries

by using state of art technologies. The modern libraries certainly cannot be passive repository for books and other printed materials. The opposite requirements of storing increasing collection in various forms and of maintaining easy access to most part of it can only be balanced by deploying information and communication technologies. Libraries should upgrade their services by digitizing their resources for online use.

These services should be accessible to anyone, regardless of time or location, through digital communication devices. Libraries can play significant role in providing a good education and knowledge of high quality. Individuals around the world, no matter how poor they may be, can access whatever knowledge and information they need by visiting libraries via the internet, such as the library of congress.

Types of information and Services provision in Library for National sustainability

In order to provide effective and efficient services to users, libraries must provide access to a broad range of information resources. Reference and referral services, orientation activities, and instruction sessions that teach users the critical thinking skills necessary for using library information resources are one of the basic services provided by the staff particularly to new users. Umoh (2017). Varied and innovative orientation programmes to new users of the library include teaching by personal contact and through the preparation and use of instructional information resources in various formats. Introducing the library users to the library activities, provide a gateway to all future inquiries, not only preparing the users as independent users but also teaching them to use information sources as citizens, as consumers, as professionals, and for recreational purposes. Moreover, the services rendered by libraries in Nigeria vary due to the nature and types of library.

Circulation/Borrowing Services

Circulation / borrowing services are one of the most vital services rendered by academic libraries in Nigeria to their clientele. These services are being provided for her teeming population of users which constitute students, staff and other potential patrons at large which are outside the academic environment such as the immediate communities' members where the library is situated. The academic library provides these services by way of providing information resources that can cater for their endeavors. Other types of library equally provide circulation/borrowing services to their users.

Reference Service

Libraries in Nigeria also provide qualitative services to the users by means of answering questions over the telephone, answering via the web or by email, answering reference questions by means of meeting face-to-face. Reference services for library users often involve not only answering specific questions but also personalized instruction in the methods of identifying and locating research information resources (Umar, 2008).

Databases, bibliographies, and other aids designed to introduce library users to the information resources the library provides and to guide them in finding the research information resources to further enrich the pool of available information resources. Reference services provided by library staff introduces the wide variety of information resources in the library system and beyond, connecting the users with branch or specialized libraries, and other supportive services including academic, financial, writing, and counseling services (Connell, 2009).

Orientation activities may take many forms, but all acquaint library users with the facilities, information resources, and services of the library system for the first time. Orientation may also include public relations activities that introduce library users to information resources available within the community or on any information network. Libraries also play some important roles with regards to reference services to its users such as assisting users to make the best selections from the universe of recorded information and to justify the existence of the library by demonstrating its value to those who support it. According to Aguolu (2002), apart from the primary functions of answering queries, the responsibilities carried out by most reference departments include the following:

- A Inter-library loan service
- B Public document service
- C Current periodical
- D Micro text and newspapers
- E Library tour
- F Library instructions
- G Book selection for the general library collection
- H Processing of theses dissertation, etc

Bibliographic Verification Services

This service involves provision of facts about publications rather than people, events or organizations. In providing this service, reference librarian searches his bibliographic tools such as indexes, bibliographies, catalogues, etc, to verify that users' information

about a document (i.e. bibliographic publication) is correct and complete. This service is very important because it is evident that students, scholars, publishers, authors and the general public sometimes miss some bibliographic information about some items they cited. Information about data of publications, correct names of authors etc is sometimes wrongly cited. This service is therefore provided to assist users to verify any of such information.

Current Awareness Services (CAS)

Many information services are provided by libraries in Nigeria especially academic libraries and the essence is to alert their users about the existence of some current publications or information. According to Madu (2009) that CAS take the form of periodic (Daily, Weekly, etc) listing of publications, monographs and periodical articles within a given subject area. These publications are circulated among some categories of users or general users of academic libraries in Nigeria in order to notify them about the existence of such information resources contained on the list. For example a user may find something relevant to its area of specialization and therefore request for the resources or a specific part of it. Elizabeth (2004) described the concept (CAS) as "The service which includes review of publications immediately upon receipt, selecting information resources pertinent to the programmes of the organization served and note individual information resources to be brought to the attention by one means or the other of those persons to whom work they are related". Information according to him can be reviewed through the following:

1. Using circulars
2. Using telephone
3. Using library bulletin
4. Using notification forms to be sent to the users
5. Routing of periodicals where relevant articles are marked to draw attention of the users
6. Circulation of table of content, etc.

Reprographic Services

The photocopying is the most frequently requested element of user services in academic libraries in Nigeria. Information resources such as reference works, rare books, theses, periodicals or heavily used items which are not normally loaned may be photocopied. Adhering strictly to copyright laws and supplied to students, some even permit the photocopying of personal document or private note. In addition, certain libraries especially academic libraries are responsible for giving binding services to the users provided that the binding unit is not overburdened with the library official work.

Extension/ community services

Apart from the aforementioned services rendered by libraries in Nigeria, they also extend their services to their immediate communities in which the academic libraries are situated. This is done by ways of providing the community users with adequate information resources that would go a long way to cater for their immediate needs and aspirations. The libraries provide services such as computer programmes designed to inculcate to the users on how to use the systems for their personal and immediate needs. They also provide books that could serve as a yardstick for education and cultural development of their society. Libraries in Nigeria also assist the community members to actualize their dreams and aspirations by providing them with information resources that would improve the quality of their lives particularly low-income individuals.

Inter-Library Co-operation

Inter-Library co-operation is another vital service rendered by libraries in Nigeria. This type of service is usually seen to be practiced between two or more libraries with mutual benefits in which the libraries involved come together with an agreement to share and exchange information resources. The IFLA Pre-Conference in Athens (Dickson and Robert, 2010), a research was conducted highlighting six libraries services in an attempt to determine their acceptance in the service context of academic libraries. These services are: RSS, instant messaging, streaming media, weblogs, tags and social networks. The findings included (but are not limited to) a rather low usage of those services, and evidence that Really Simple Syndication (RSS) was the only widely used web service among the six, and tags was the least used. The integration of a specific set of services is re-examined after two years, a period of time that can provide some clues as to the state of affairs in the field of academic libraries and the incorporation of web services.

The implementation of several web services was recorded, showing an increase in provision but at the same time, there was not a corresponding increase in user participation in several of these services. Consequently, these services may not have the anticipated impact on the strategic service plans of libraries, the purpose was to document the usage of twelve library services: the six services mentioned above with the addition of Face book, Twitter, web site interface for mobile devices, reference service via SMS, YouTube and browser toolbars.

Technical Services

Under the technical services, libraries in Nigeria are seen as providing some technical services to their users. Gbaje (2007) highlights some of those services as follow:

1. Cataloguing and classification: The libraries in Nigeria provide both manual and electronic cataloguing systems for their users that facilitate easy access to the information resources of their choice in the library. Librarians make impact in this area by suggesting a suitable classification system to be used in the library. The section also advises the cataloguers to include some information while cataloguing in order to provide useful information about information resources on the catalogue cards so as to assist users in locating information resources easily.
2. Acquisition / collection management: The libraries in Nigeria acquire, collect and manage the information resources (books and media) as well as making these information resources available for their users in order to meet up with their information needs.

ICT facilities as Enabler for facilitating information services in Libraries

As pointed out by Aina (2004), it is generally known that the library and information profession borrows from a number of disciplines, such as sociology, psychology, computer science, business management, mathematics, statistics, marketing, etc. Thus, anything that impacts on any of these disciplines would have a direct influence on library and information science profession. Information and communication technology (ICT) has radically transformed most of the services provided by a library. ICT is heavily utilized in the storage, processing and dissemination of information. Like a cyclone, the technology-driven environment has enveloped the library and is taken in to unprecedented heights in knowledge acquisition, management, and communication. Even, the vocabulary of librarianship is changing: "dissemination" is being replaced by "communication" "repository" by "database", "literature" by "knowledge", "search" by "navigation", etc. This reflects current approach to packaging and the tools used for managing knowledge. Knowledge itself has become more ubiquitous than was ever imagined twenty years ago. Any modern library and information professional must be knowledgeable in library automation, networking, Internet surfing, data base management, processing software, statistical software, etc.

All these services, which must be made available in the libraries, can be regarded as necessary tools for any developing country to engage in capacity building for that country to have a meaningful development. It must be realized that for a successful capacity building concept, one does not have to leave the site of work before one could be professionally developed. It is imperative that a professional or a worker must keep

pace with the latest development in the profession. For instance, the concept of "traditional librarian" is no longer tenable. Changes in the profession are happening both in magnitude and diversity. Correspondingly, the role of the librarian is changing, thus librarian and other professional must transform themselves and the society through training and retraining in other to meet the expectations of their changing role. Professional development has been described as more or less a life-long process, where individuals are exposed to changes all the time. Professional development or capacity building is mainly for personal and career advancement and improvement of any organization. Hence, professionals do not need to wait for sponsorship before they can develop themselves and this can be done by cultivating the idea of making use of the library facilities in their environment.

Conclusion

Capacity building libraries in Nigeria is a necessity for better national sustainability. This paper concludes that information services library contribute immensely in shaping the academic and social aspect of the library users, library staff and the library collection. Libraries had been performed many important roles in the past agrarian and industrial societies. The paper concludes that the difference services rendered by libraries have positive effect in capacity building on national sustainability. In order to satisfy user's information needs, libraries store all kinds and forms of material and information and disseminate beyond the geographical boundaries. Today's advanced information technology have facilitate in the provision of this services and assist libraries to accomplish their immense objectives.

References

Abubakar, G.B. (2004). "Libraries as Tools for Promoting Education in the Society: An analysis of Library Utilization by Women in Kano State Public Libraries". Paper Presented at Nigerian Library Association 42nd National Conference and AGM, June 20 - 25, 2004, held at Akure, Nigeria, pp. 19.

Aguolu, C. C. (2002), Libraries and Information Management in Nigeria: Seminal Essay on themes and problems. Maiduguri

Aina, L. O. (2004). Coping with the Challenges of Library and Information Services Delivery: The Need for Institutionalized Professional Development. Paper Presented at

the Nigerian Library Association 42nd National Conference and AGM, June 20 – 25, 2004, held at Akure, Nigeria., pp. 4.

Anand, R. (2018). *Capacity Building of Library Professionals in the Digital Environment A Study of Universities of Karnataka State*. Karnatak University. Retrieved from: <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/224971>

Bolger, J. (2000). "Capacity Development: Why, What and How in Capacity Development". *Occasional series*. Vol.1, no. 1, May 2000. CIDA, Policy Branch. Canadian International Development Agency

Connell, R. S. (2009), "Academic libraries, Facebook and MySpace, and student outreach: a survey of student opinion", portal: *Libraries and the Academy*, 9 (1): 25-36.

Dickson, A. and Robert, P. H. (2010), "Social networking in academic libraries: the possibilities and the concerns", *New Library World*, 111 (11/12): 468-479.

Gbaje, E. S. (2007) "Provision of online information services in Nigerian Academic Libraries. *Nigerian Library Association*, Vol. 40, 1-16

Mabawonku, I. (2005). "Capacity Building for the Sustenance of Library Consortia in Africa Universities Libraries," in Proceeding of SCAUL-WA. Senegal: Dakar

Madu, E. C. (2009) *Technology for Management and Services: Modern Libraries and Information Centers in Developing Countries*. Ibadan: Evi-Coleman Publication.

Ogunmodede, T. and Mafelu, M. (2012) "Capacity Building Programmes for Library Staff in University of Ibadan and University of Lagos Libraries," *Samaru Journal of Information Studies* 12, no. 1& 2: 61

Ogunsola, L.A. (2011) *Libraries as Tools for Capacity Building in Developing Countries*. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 605. Available at <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/605>

The University of Memphis (2020). *Benefits of Capacity Building*. Accessed on 16/1/2021, Available <https://www.memphis.edu/ess/module5/page7.php>

Umar, G. G. (2008) Reference and Information Services Delivery and the Utilization of ICTs in University Libraries in Nigeria. Apani Pub, Kaduna.

Umoh, E.B. (2017) Information and Services Provision by Academic Libraries in Nigeria. *Inter. J. Acad. Lib. Info. Sci.* 5(5): 153-159